

BASES OF ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Dilkhumor Oltinbekova

UzSWLU, Third English faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7316477>

Abstract. *By teaching materials in this article, I mean all the materials included in the EMC (teaching and methodological kit), which is used as the main one when taking an English lesson at school. The article gives a hint to young teachers when using the teaching material during the lesson.*

Keywords: *UMK, diagnostic tests, module, material adaptation Most modern EMC consists of a large number of components. Often.*

ОСНОВЫ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Под учебно-методическими материалами в данной статье я имею в виду все материалы, входящие в УМК (учебно-методический комплект), который используется в качестве основного при проведении урока английского языка в школе. В статье дается подсказка молодым учителям при использовании учебного материала на уроке.*

Ключевые слова: *УМК, диагностические тесты, модуль, материальная адаптация Большинство современных ЭМК состоит из большого количества компонентов. Часто.*

The teaching materials include a teacher's book, a book for classroom work, a notebook for homework, an audio CD for exercises, a DVD with video or interactive assignments, photocopied materials, an online resource with additional assignments, a mini-dictionary, and so on. When choosing basic and additional teaching materials, the teacher proceeds from the needs of the students, their level of language proficiency and interests. Questionnaires, interviews and diagnostic tests can be used to identify needs.

What questions to ask when choosing learning materials?

The teacher does not always have the opportunity to choose a textbook on his own, but can always decide which materials from an existing textbook to use in class. When choosing study materials, it is worth asking yourself the following questions:

- Is the material appropriate for the needs, ages and interests of the students?
- Are the course materials appropriate for the level?
- Will the students be interested in the topics proposed for discussion?
- How much are the tutorial topics explained? What are the exercises for them? And assignments?
- How well is the material organized? Can you understand the "logic" of filing material, can you quickly navigate the textbook and find the necessary section or module?

If something does not suit you, then you can either replace the materials (taking similar ones from other textbooks), or adapt them, that is, change them so that they fit the students.

The following strategies can be used to adapt the material:

Add material. If there are too few tasks, and you understand that students

If more practice is needed, you can find similar tasks in other textbooks, or compose them yourself.

Shrink the material. If the assignment is too long, or too many similar assignments are included in the textbook, you can use only part of the material and skip the rest. You can also divide the assignment into several parts and give each student (or group of students) their part of the assignment.

Change material level. If the task is too complicated, then you can simplify it. For example, splitting a long text into several parts, reading and discussing one in class, and asking others to read at home.

Regroup material. You can change the order of the tasks in the tutorial.

Change the type of task. For example, instead of answering questions about the text, you can print the text on separate sheets, cut it into paragraphs, and ask students to put the paragraphs in the correct order.

On a note.

Sometimes it makes sense to skip a module or part of a module, but you shouldn't do so too often. Students mostly use the textbook to review material, and if there is too much of the missing material, they can become confused.

If you use a lot of additional material, be sure to talk to the students

about how to store it correctly. If the materials are paper, make sure students put them in a special folder. If you share links to online resources with students, tell them how best to organize them.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2013 yil 8 maydagi "Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining chet tillar bo'yicha Davlat standartlarini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi 124 – sonli qarori.
2. Ersoz, A. (2000) EFL / ESL sinfida oltita o'yin. Internet TESL jurnali, jild. VI, №6.
3. Carrier, Maykl va Britaniya o'qituvchilari markazi (1980) .Til o'rganuvchilar uchun o'yinlar va tadbirlar, London